

How do I reach these kids?!

Reimagining student worker management

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Background

Rosalind Franklin University

- 6 Colleges
 - Medicine
 - Health Professions
 - Nursing
 - Pharmacy
 - Podiatry
 - Graduate and Postdoctoral Studies

Boxer Library

- 19 Staff Members
 - 1 AVP
 - 1 Director
 - 4 Librarians
 - 1 Library Associate
 - 2 Library Assistants
 - 10 Library Aides*

The Mission

Library Aide Manager

- ✓ *Manage current Library Aides*
- ✓ *Hire new students as needed*
- ✓ *Train Library Aides once hired*
- ✓ *Maintain circulation desk coverage*

Cracks

- Current Library Aides
 - Away from circulation desk
 - Not emailing patrons
 - Not checking drop box for returns
- Future Library Aides
 - No hiring process
 - No process to address performance issues

Goals

- Education
 - Leadership/Management training

IGNITE COLLABORATION:
THRIVING MULTIGENERATIONAL LIBRARIES

Student Workers \neq Kids

Student Workers = Adults

Goals

- Education
 - Leadership/Management training
- Management
 - Everyone understands job expectations
 - Increase job morale
 - Maintain enthusiasm

Changes Made

- Job expectations
- Job checklist
- Library aide interest form
- Interview process
- Increased presence
- Showing more appreciation

Interested in working at the library?

Library Aide Interest Form

Student Spotlight

This summer, we're taking a moment to celebrate two valuable members of our student library team, Anita Kalatoor and Elizabeth Fink, who will soon be graduating! Anita has been a Library Aide for over a year while Elizabeth became a Library Aide in January. Both Anita and Elizabeth are part of the Master of Entry into Nursing Practice (MENP) program at the College of Nursing.

Moving Forward

- Occasional coaching
- Set tone for employment
 - 7 hired this Fall
- 19 not 9 staff
- Department Hierarchy
 - coming soon

Takeaway

- How do you reach these kids?
 - Remember they're not kids

Questions?

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Thank you!

